

Eco-Labeling and Consumer Buying Behaviour of Fast Moving Consumer Goods (FMCGS) In Akwa Ibom State

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Abstract: *The purpose of this study was to investigate the impact of eco-labeling on the purchasing patterns of consumers of fast-moving consumer goods (FMCGs) in Akwa Ibom, Nigeria. Awareness of the environment, symbols of recycling, and visual components were the variables that were taken into consideration. Three hypotheses were developed. A survey research methodology was chosen, and the convenience sampling approach was utilized to select 384 respondents from the fast-moving consumer goods industry in Akwa Ibom. The data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics, and the simple linear regression model was utilized to test all hypotheses at a level of significance of 0.05. It was found, from the findings of the study that eco-awareness, recycling symbols, and visual elements all had a substantial and favorable association with the purchasing behavior of consumers of FMCGs. Consumer purchasing behavior of FMCGs in Akwa Ibom State was found to be significantly and positively influenced by eco-awareness, recycling symbols, and visual elements. One of the recommendations was that businesses should add eco-awareness messages into their product packaging and marketing materials in order to highlight the environmental benefits that come with selecting sustainable products.*

Keywords: *Eco-labeling, Awareness of the environment, Symbols of recycling, Visual components, Consumer behavior*

INTRODUCTION

Background

Universities, businesses, and governments in both emerging and developed countries have had disagreements about how to protect the environment and make it last. Buying, making products, marketing, and responding to corporate strategy issues in a way that supports sustainable growth are things that businesses around the world do. Acee-Eke and Nwokah (2019) say that as people around the world become more worried about climate change and sustainability, they are looking for ways to connect the things they buy with actions that are good for the environment. These changes in how people act have made eco-labeling programmes more important, especially for FMCGs (Sharma, 2000). Consumers are more likely to buy green goods when they know about their green features through eco-labeling or eco-certification (Young, Hwang, McDonald, & Qates, 2018). People can use environmental or eco-labels to help them pick items that are good for the

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environment. Businesses often use it to set their goods apart, promote them, and send the message that they are eco-friendly.

Green marketing, also called ecological marketing, means that companies should act ethically (Ibok & Mfon, 2019) and environmentally friendly when dealing with customers, suppliers, dealers, and workers. To meet the wants of people who care about the environment, green marketing means making and selling goods that are eco-friendly. Kotler and Armstrong (2016) said that these kinds of goods should meet certain environmental standards, like having recyclable and reusable packaging, better ways to stop pollution, and activities that use less energy. The act of promoting things and services that are better for the environment is called "green marketing." It includes a lot of different marketing actions, like changing the way a product is made, making the packaging more eco-friendly, and changing how adverts are made (Odiah, 2017).

The American Marketing Association defines environmentally friendly marketing as the promotion of goods that are thought to be safe for the environment. This can also be called ecological marketing or green marketing. Green marketing, then, is the act of promoting goods and services based on how well they treat the earth. This means that their benefits must not hurt the environment. So, the logical assumption behind green marketing is that people will see a product's greenness as a benefit and choose to buy it based on that (Ibok & Etuk, 2014).

According to Taiwo and Matthew (2019), and Awah, Mfon and Ibok (2024), consumer buying behaviour includes the thoughts, feelings, and actions people have when they choose, buy, use, and get rid of things and services to meet their needs and wants. Mfon (2021), summarises the behaviour of consumers as their responses to communications and brands. Chinda and Umeh (2023) say that "green consumers" are people who care about society and the earth and choose to buy things that are good for both. Green consumers pay attention to both the eco-friendly ingredients and the eco-friendly packaging. This is because packages have recently been found to be the main source of environmental pollution.

As part of green marketing efforts, marketing companies now try to teach customers about the benefits of eco-labelling products. Eco-awareness, recycling symbols, and claims that a product is free of chemicals are some of the new green marketing tactics that companies are using. So, using green marketing strategies is important to change people's minds and get them to buy goods with eco-labels (Maheshwari, 2014). With this as a starting point, the scholars looked into how people in Akwa Ibom State choose to buy eco-labeled FMCGs.

Statement of the Problem

Some of the environmental problems our country is facing right now are air pollution, bad water quality, plastics that damage the environment, and the need to quickly cut down on energy waste. Because people are becoming more concerned about the environment and how it affects their physical and mental health, a lot of work needs to be done to make firms and customers more aware of the problem and change people's attitudes in order to create an eco-friendly and sustainable environment through eco-labeling.

A lot of research has been done on the relationship between eco-labeling and how people buy FMCGs in many areas and countries around the world. These studies have used factors like eco-awareness, recycling marks, and visual elements. In spite of this, there is not enough research on how eco-labeling strategies (like eco-awareness, recycling marks, and visual elements) might change how people in Akwa Ibom State buy FMCGs

With this in mind, the goal of this study was to look at how eco-labeling (eco-awareness, recycling symbols, and the visual aspect) affects people's buying habits of FMCGs in Akwa Ibom State.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study was to determine the effect of eco-labeling on consumer buying behaviour of FMCGs in Akwa Ibom state. The specific objectives were to:

- i. Ascertain the effect of eco-awareness on consumer buying behaviour of FMCGs in Akwa Ibom State.
- ii. Determine the effect of recycling symbols on consumer buying behaviour of FMCGs in Akwa Ibom State.
- iii. Investigate the effect of visual elements on consumer behaviour of FMCGs in Akwa Ibom State.

Research Questions

- i. What is the effect of eco-awareness on consumer buying behaviour of FMCGs in Akwa Ibom State?
- ii. What is the effect of recycling symbols on consumer buying behaviour of FMCGs in Akwa Ibom State?
- iii. What is the effect of visual elements on consumer buying behaviour of FMCGs in Akwa Ibom State?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested in the study:

HO₁: Eco-awareness has no significant effect on consumer buying behaviour of FMCGs in Akwa Ibom State.

HO₂: Recycling symbols have no significant effect on consumer buying behaviour of FMCGs in Akwa Ibom State.

HO₃: Visual elements have no significant effect on consumer buying behaviour of FMCGs in Akwa Ibom State.

Review of Literature

An overview of the concept of Eco-label strategy

Different ideas have been put forward to explain the word "eco-label" or "eco-labelling." Lefebure and Munoz (2011) say that eco-labelling is the process of advertising items that are good for the environment. They also said that it is a standard sticker that shoppers use to find out if an item is sustainable before they buy it. The words "eco-labeling" and "environmental labeling" were used interchangeably by Borin and Cert (2011) in their work to describe information that a product gives about the environmental effects of its production or use. We define eco-labeling as labels or tags on products that show they are environmentally friendly or have been made in a way that does not harm the environment.

Labelling or eco-friendly product strategy is an effective way to sell in a green way. Eco-labels are a good way to let customers know how the things they buy affect the earth (Orsato, 2009). McCluskey and Loureiro (2003) say that eco-labels find products that are better for the environment by comparing how they affect the environment to other goods in the same category. McCluskey and Loureiro (2003) say that eco-labels are market-oriented because they are not directly regulated by the government but do require standard compliance.

The environmental impact assessment looks at how goods are made, how they are used, and how they are thrown away. Labelling or certification of eco-products tells customers about the green features of the product and encourages them to buy green goods (Young, Hwang, McDonald & Oates, 2010). These are signs, symbols, or logos for environmental protection or eco-certifications that

show a product or service meets certain standards for sustainability and the environment set by a separate group or authority. Usually, these labels are put on products to help people make better, more eco-friendly buying choices. But it is not clear how well eco-product labels work, especially for people who do not know much about sustainability problems and might not understand what they say. Also, buyers have a hard time telling the difference between labels for eco-friendly products and regular ones. Acee-Eke and Nwokah (2019) say that eco-labels do not work as well when people do not know about them or accept them.

According to Thøgersen (2000), eco-labeling on products can successfully convince people to pick products that are good for the environment. People might be ready to pay more for goods that have extra benefits, like high quality, safe for the environment, organic ingredients, and packaging that is not dangerous. Thøgersen (2000) says that eco-friendly product labels use logos to let customers know how their purchases will affect the environment. This is what Grant (2007) says about eco-product labels: they help people choose goods that are better for the environment. Porto, Malandrino, and Supino (2010) say that an eco-label is a product claim that gives customers reliable and easy-to-find information about how a product affects the environment.

The literature talks about different aspects of eco-label product strategy, such as educating consumers, making them eco-aware, using recycling symbols, making claims that the product is chemical-free, following the rules, and coming up with new ideas. For this study, eco-awareness, recycling symbols, and visual elements were used as stand-ins for eco-label product strategy elements that are likely to affect how people buy things.

Eco-awareness

As a part of eco-label product strategy and consumer buying behaviour, eco-awareness is the degree to which people are aware of and understand environmental issues and sustainability when they are making buying choices. Eco-awareness is the understanding or knowledge that people have about the importance of protecting the environment and the impact their choices have on it. Kollmuss and Agyeman (2002) opine that environmental awareness is made up of two parts: a cognitive part that is based on understanding and a sensory part that is based on perception. As a general term, "ecological awareness" refers to the growing level of social awareness that shows up in people's thoughts and experiences, as well as their ways of living, judging, and comprehending the biosphere (Olsen, 2014).

In the same way, Cruz and Tantengco (2017) and Jakobi and Schwartz (2012) say that environmental education lets people learn about environmental problems, work to solve them, and take action to protect and repair the environment. This helps people learn more about environmental problems and give them the tools they need to make smart, responsible choices. People would care more about their environmental impact if they knew the bad effects of the things they do every day and how those effects are felt by the environment (Olsen, 2014). Being aware of the environment is a key part of figuring out how eco-label product plan affects how people buy things. It means making choices based on good information, believing in eco-labels, and making choices that are in line with one's personal views.

Recycling Symbols

Recycling marks are an important part of eco-labeling strategies because they affect what people buy. These marks are often found on product packaging to let people know about how recyclable the materials are and to encourage people to act in ways that are good for the environment. Thus,

these researchers define recycling symbols are signs or logos on product or packaging that indicate the item can be recycled, and is environmentally friendly.

When talking about eco-label product strategy, D'souza, Taghian, and Lamb (2006) say that "recycling symbols" are standard pictures on product packages that show how recyclable the materials are or how good they are for the environment. As a strategic tool, these symbols help manufacturers to show that they care about the environment, so customers can make decisions that are in line with their values. The authors also said that marketers let people know about the environmental benefits of their goods in a number of ways. One way is by using general or specific product claims on labels, such as "ecofriendly," "environmentally safe," "recyclable," "biodegradable," and "ozone-friendly."

It is interesting to note that some Nigerian companies, like Nestle Nigeria Plc, Promasidor Nigeria Limited, GlaxoSmithKline Consumer Nigeria Plc, UAC Foods Limited, and others, use eco-labels and recycling symbols in their production. For example, the labels of their products say things like "Recyclable," "Help keep Nigeria tidy," "Keep our environment clean," and "dispose properly."

As a part of eco-label product plan, recycling symbols are a visual and symbolic language that affects how people think and act. These symbols are cues that let people know that the product is eco-friendly and encourage them to do things that are good for the earth, like recycling. This dimension shows how marketing strategies and consumers' concern for the environment affect each other, leading people to choose goods that are in line with sustainable practices (Thorgeresen, 2000).

Visual Elements

According to Kotler *et al* (2019), when designing a package, there are six things that must be thought about: the size, shape, material, colour, text, and name. Each of these aspects of packaging affects a customer's decision to buy in a different way. Silayoi and Speece (2004) say that when makers and designers make a product label, they should think about six things: the size, colour, graphics material, flavour, and how the product is packaged.

These researchers consider that these six features of packing can be broken down into two groups: visual and informational elements. The graphics, size, colour, and form of the package make up the visual characteristic, which has to do with the emotional side of decision-making. The informational parts, on the other hand, have to do with the data and technology in the package and are more likely to deal with the thinking side of decisions. Thus, they define visual elements are images, colours, and symbols on products or packaging that catch the eye and convey specific environmentally friendly information to consumers.

When talking about eco-label product strategy and customer buying behaviour, visual elements are the graphic or design parts of eco-labels that affect how people see them and what they decide to buy. According to Tang, Fryxell, and Chow (2004), visual elements are things like the size, colour, or logos that are put on goods to show that they are eco-friendly, organic, or sustainable. How people see eco-labeled goods and how they decide to buy them is greatly affected by the visual elements that are used. Eco-labels can become more credible, visible, and appealing with good design, which will eventually lead people to buy environmentally friendly products.

Fast Moving Consumer Goods (FMCGs)

Consumer goods that are bought and sold quickly and for a low price are called fast moving consumer goods (FMCG). These are usually things that people buy a lot. Customer packaged goods (CPG) is another name for these items. FMCG includes a lot of different things that people use every day and that usually do not last long (Kotler & Keller, 2016). Food and drinks, personal care items,

home cleaning supplies, cosmetics and beauty products, tobacco, over-the-counter medicines, and other things are all examples of FMCGs

Eco-label Product Strategy and Consumer Buying Behaviour

The eco-label product plan is a way to talk about the environment and get people to behave in ways that are better for the environment (Taufique, Vcino&Polonsky, 2016). D'Souza *et al.* (2006) say that environmental labels help people pick items that are good for the environment. Businesses often use it to set their goods apart, promote them, and send the message that they are eco-friendly. Taufique *et al.*, (2016) also said that marketers tell people about the environmental benefits of their products in a number of ways. One way is through general or specific claims on product labels, such as “ecofriendly”, “environmentally safe”, “recyclable”, “biodegradable” and “ozone-friendly”. So, an eco-label is a standard sign that tells people who are planning to buy something about how sustainable it is (Lefebure & Munoz, 2011).

Consumers are the people who buy and use goods and services. It includes all the people, groups, and families that buy things for their own use. Sometimes a customer is adaptable, crazy, and hard to predict. Other times, they may be reasonable and nice. Meeting the wants of the customer is still the most important thing for a business (Nwaizugbo & Ogbunankwor, 2013). Chinda and Umeh (2023) say that "green consumers" are people who care about society and the earth and choose to buy things that are good for both. That's why people often call them "environmentally conscious shoppers." These customers care about the environment, and it shows in the things they buy and use. For example, they choose biodegradable or reusable items that would not pollute or hurt the environment, which protects the ecosystem for future generations.

Figure 1: Conceptual Model of Eco-labeling and Consumer Buying Behaviour

Source: Researchers' Conceptualisation, (2024).

Theoretical Framework

The idea behind this study came from Ajzen's theory of planned behaviour, which he came up with in 1985. The theory attempts to guess how people will buy things that are in high demand. The idea of planned behaviour is often used to explain what people want and how they behave in the market for goods. Souri, Sajjadian, Sheikh, and Sana (2018) and Zheng, Siddik, Masukujjaman, Alam and Akter, (2020) used the theory of planned behaviour to explain why people want to buy things. Auliandri, Thoyib, Rohman, and Rofiq (2018) say that new study backs up the theory of planned behaviour as a good way to understand and predict why people will choose to buy green packaged goods. This study adds to the behaviour and intentions model, which is a theory of planned behaviour, by looking at customer buying behaviour using separate variables such as eco-awareness, recycling symbols, and visual elements.

Review of Empirical Literature

Several studies have been done on the effect of eco-label product strategy as it relates to consumer buying intentions. Some of the studies are shown below:

D'souza, Taghian, and Lamb (2006) did a real-world study on how environmental labels affect people. The researchers' goal was to find out how consumers understand labels and how consumers with different levels of environmental concern react to labels. A sample of 155 consumers was asked to fill out the poll. The study that used both descriptive measures and correlations between factors found that some people have trouble understanding product labels. In the end, they said that companies should make sure that labels are clear, correct, and easy to read so that customers are happy with the information on them and how they communicate.

Ibok and Etuk (2014) did a study on the demographic and socioeconomic factors that affect green intake. The study's goal was to find out the racial and socioeconomic makeup of "green consumers" and how those traits affect the actions that are good for the earth. A survey was given to 102 people in Akwa Ibom State who were part of the green squad. According to the results, most "green" consumers who act in ways that are good for the world are college graduates. They are mostly middle-class guys with white-collar jobs who are married and own their own homes. They put environmental safety and security at the top of their list when deciding what to buy and how to get rid of their trash. Their results also show that a consumers' age, family income, home ownership, employment status, buying habits, level of education, and where they live all have a statistically significant effect on how responsible they are as consumers. They came to the conclusion that making people more aware of safe environments will make them more concerned about their socioeconomic and demographic status.

Kuvykaite, Dovaliene, and Navickiene (2009) looked into how the words and pictures on a package affected the buyer. Both of the factors were thought to be very important. Accordingly, the most important thing to look at when buying milk was the size. Even though colour was important, it was not seen as very important in relation to other people. The images and logos were also seen as less important, but the information about the products was seen as important. Kuvykaite, Dovaliene, and Navickiene (2009) also looked into how these package features affected shoppers who were pressed for time and shoppers who were not pressed for time. Both times, the researchers found that verbal (informational) package aspects were more important than visual ones.

Alabo and Anyasor (2021) investigated green marketing and the long-term viability of Nigerian brewers for the purpose of determining whether or not they may be successful. The concept of how innovations spread was the cornerstone of the research project. Through the use of a descriptive

survey methodology, a sample size of 324 individuals was utilized. For the purpose of the study, primary data was collected through the use of a standardized questionnaire. At that point, the assumptions were put to the test by conducting an analysis of the data using frequency tables, percentages, and multiple regression analysis. The factors of the study, which included green product, green price, green place (distribution), and green marketing, were found to have a significant and favorable relationship with the sustainability of breweries in the southeastern region of Nigeria. In the end, they came to the realization that environmentally conscious marketing has a significant and favorable impact on the long-term profitability of breweries located in the southeastern region of Nigeria. Therefore, the researchers recommended that breweries in South-East Nigeria and other locations should continue to fulfill their environmental responsibilities and pay greater attention to issues that are associated with this in order to ensure that their businesses are able to continue operating.

In their 2017 study, Ayodele, Panama, and Akemu investigated the impact that green information had on post-graduate students at Nnamdi Azikiwe University in Awka, Nigeria, who intended to purchase environmentally friendly electrical products. The design of the study was a survey, and there were 345 people selected to take part in the research. They utilized questionnaire and stratified random sampling. For the purpose of testing the hypotheses, multiple regression analysis was utilized. Customers' concerns about the environment, the influence of green friends and family, and the strength of the brand all had a positive and statistically significant impact on their intentions to purchase environmentally friendly devices, according to the findings of the study. As a result, they arrived at the conclusion that people's intentions to purchase environmentally friendly devices are positively influenced by their awareness of the environment, which is a major and positive effect. These individuals made a number of recommendations, one of which was that the government of Nigeria should make use of its regulatory authorities in order to ensure that people adhere to the law and are aware of how to behave in a manner that is ecologically beneficial.

Methodology

Research Design

The survey research design was adopted for the study. This design was chosen to help the researcher get information directly from the respondents.

Population and Sample

The study's group was all people in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, who bought fast-moving consumer goods. A pilot poll of 50 copies of questionnaire was done to get the sample size. Of these, 26 could be used, while 24 could not be used, which is 52% and 48%, respectively, using the Topman formula. This formula was chosen so that the researcher could get a good sample number for the study.

Topman formula: $n = Z^2pq/e^2$

Where n= Sample size

Z = standard deviation for desired test of confidence (1.96)

P= probability of positive response (52% or 0.52)

Q= probability of negative response (48% or 0.48)

E= 5% limit error (0.05)

Therefore, $n = 1.96^2 (0.52 \times 0.48) / 0.05^2 = 3.8416 \times 0.52 \times 0.48 / 0.0025 = \frac{0.95886336}{0.0025} = 383.54$

n = 384

Sampling Technique

The researchers used the convenience sampling method to pick 384 people from Akwa Ibom State's three senatorial districts (Uyo, Ikot Ekpene, and Eket) to take part in the study. This method afforded the researchers the privilege of picking those they deemed capable of providing the required data by filling the questionnaire accurately. Some of the sites that these respondents were picked from included grocery stores, markets, cosmetics stores, and some food stores in the key towns of Uyo, Ikot Ekpene, and Eket because they were easy to reach and had a lot of fast-moving consumer goods' customers.

Research Instrument

A structured questionnaire was used to gather information. There were two parts to the questionnaire: A and B. In Section A, the respondents' personal information was listed. In Section B, four-point adjusted Likert scale statements were used to measure the constructs.

Validity of the Instrument

Two copies of the instrument were given to two research experts in Akwa Ibom State University to ascertain its validity. These experts made the necessary additions and deletion to the statements, which were then added to the final copy that was printed and given out.

Table 1 Cronbach's Alpha Pre-test result

Variables	No of items	Reliability coefficient
Eco awareness	3	0.801
Recycling symbols	3	0.799
Visual elements	3	0.860
Buying behaviour	3	0.756
Total	12	0.804

From Table1, the reliability scores for all variables were above the 0.7 threshold of acceptable Cronbach Alpha value. Thus, the instrument was considered reliable.

Method of Data Analysis

Simple percentages and frequency counts were used to analyse the respondents' personal information, and simple regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses. We tested all our hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance.

Table 2: Questionnaire Administration

Items	Number of Questionnaire	Percentage (%)
Usable	371	96.61
Un-usable	13	3.39
Total	384	100

Table 2 shows that out of the 384 copies of the questionnaire that were sent to respondents, 371 were returned in a form that could be used. This means that 96.61% of them were returned in usable form. The other 13 copies (3.39%) were either returned but not in a form that could be used or were not returned at all.

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Table 3: Demographic Profile of Respondents

Variables	Respondents	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	179	48.2
Female	192	51.8
Total	371	100.0
Age		
15-24	105	28.3
25-34	147	39.6
35-44	76	20.5
45 and Above	43	11.6
Total	371	100.0
Educational Qualification		
SSCE	85	22.9
ND/NCE	104	28.0
HND/BSc	112	30.2
Above BSc	70	18.9
Total	371	100.0
Occupation		
Employed	192	51.8
Unemployed	179	48.2
Total	371	100.0

The demographic information in Table 3 shows that 179 of the respondents were men (48.2%), and 192 were women, (51.8%). The difference in the number of men to women in the sample population did not change the results in any way. Instead, it shows how the questionnaire was purposefully distributed within the sample population. The table also shows that 105 respondents (28.3%), were between the ages of 15 and 24; 147 respondents(39.6%), were between the ages of 25 and 34; 76 respondents (20.5 %), were between the ages of 35 and 44, and 43 respondents (11.6%), were 45 years or older. This means that the people who answered were old enough to understand the issues being studied and could make important contributions to the study as a whole.

The table also shows that 85 respondents (22.9%), had an SSC; 104 respondents (28%), had an ND/NCE; 112 respondents (30.2%), had an HND/BSc, and 70 respondents (18.9%), had an educational certificate higher than a BSc. So, we could say that the people who responded to the questionnaire were literate enough to understand the issues that were addressed in the study. The results in the table also showed that 192 respondents (51.8%) were employed while 179 people (48.2%), were unemployed. This means that most people who answered made money and can buy FMCG goods.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis one

H01: Eco-awareness has no significant effect on consumer buying behaviour of FMCGs in Akwa Ibom State.

Table 4: Model summary of simple linear regression showing the effect of eco-awareness and consumer buying behaviour.

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.611a	0.776	0.775	1.48172

a. Predictors: (Constant), Eco-awareness

It can be seen in table 4 that the dependent and independent factors are linked by the R value of 0.881. With an R-Square value of 0.776, eco-awareness was able to explain about 77.6% of the differences in how people bought things. The F-calculated number of 1278.335 means that the model worked well. If the independent variable (eco-awareness) stays the same, the constant number of 29.425 means that the buying habits of consumers will stay the same. The eco-awareness index was 0.687, which means that a one-unit change in eco-awareness will cause a 0.687-unit change in how people buy things. A P-value of 0.000 means that eco-awareness had a statistically significant effect on how people bought things.

Test of Hypothesis Two

H02: Recycling symbols have no significant effect on consumer buying behaviour of FMCGs in Akwa Ibom State.

Table 5: Model summary of simple linear regression showing the effect of recycling symbols on consumer buying behaviour

Model summary				
Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.876a	0.767	0.766	1.51098

Predictors: (Constant), Recycling Symbols

With an R value of 0.876, the result shows that there is a strong effect of the independent factor on the dependent factor. With an R-Square value of 0.767, the recycling marks could explain about 76.7 percent of the differences in how people bought things. The model worked well, as shown by the F-calculated number of 1215.164 at 0.000. The number of 29.408 means that if the independent variable (recycling symbols) stays the same, the way people buy things will stay at 29.408. Recycling symbols had a value of 0.694, which means that a change of one unit in these symbols will cause a change of one unit in how people buy things. A P-value of 0.000 means that recycling marks did have a statistically significant effect on how people bought FMCGs

Test of Hypothesis Three

H03: Visual elements have no significant effect on consumer buying behaviour of FMCGs in Akwa Ibom State.

Table 6: Model summary of simple linear regression showing the relationship of visual element with consumer buying behaviour

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R ²	Std Error of Estimate
1	0.864	0.747	0.747	1.57393

a. Predictors: (Constant), Visual elements

The R value of 0.864 in table 6 shows that there is a strong effect of the independent variable on the dependent factor. With an R-Square value of 0.747, visual factors explained about 74.7 percent of the differences in how people bought things. The number of 1090.972 for F calculated at 0.000 means that the model was good. The number of 29.491 means that if the independent variable (visual elements) stays the same, the way people buy things will stay at 29.491. The coefficient for the visual element was 0.688, which means that a change of one unit in the visual element will cause a change of one unit in the way people buy things. A P-value of 0.000 means that the visual part had a statistically significant effect on how people bought things.

Discussion of findings

The main goal of this study was to find out how eco-labeling changes people's choices about what (FMCGs) to buy in Akwa Ibom State. Eco-awareness, recycling symbols, and visual elements dimensions were all tried to see how they affected people's decisions to buy. The test of hypothesis one (H0₁) showed that eco-awareness is significantly linked to people in Akwa Ibom state buying more FMCGs, with an R-square value of 0.776 and a p-value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05. This result supports what Panama, Amos, and Akemu (2017) found, which is that being aware of the environment has a good and significant effect on people's plans to buy environmentally friendly electronics.

The test of hypothesis two (H0₂) also showed that recycling symbols have a strong positive relationship with how people in Akwa Ibom State buy FMCGs, with an R-square value of 0.767 and a p-value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05. This result fits with what D'souza, Taghian, and Lamb (2006) found: for customers to be satisfied with the accuracy of the information on labels, they need to be clear, accurate, and easy to read.

The test of hypothesis three (H0₃) showed that visual elements have a strong, positive relationship with how people in Akwa Ibom state buy FMCGs, with an R-square value of 0.747 and a p-value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05. This result agrees with what Kuvykaite, Dovaliene, and Navickiene found in their 2009 study, which showed that both the visual and verbal parts of a package can influence a consumer's decision to buy.

Conclusion

The results obtained from the analysis of hypothesis one, led to the conclusion that eco-awareness is a significant positive predictor of FMCGs buying activity in Akwa Ibom State, as the p-value was less than 0.05 (Sig. p-value = 0.000 < 0.05). From the test of hypothesis two, we can say that recycling symbols are a strong indicator of people's buying habits for FMCGs in Akwa Ibom State,

since the p-value is less than 0.05 ($\hat{u} = 0.000$). The p-value for hypothesis three is less than 0.05, which means that it is statistically significant. This means that the visual elements present a strong prediction of how people in Akwa Ibom State will buy FMCGs.

Recommendations

On the basis of the findings, the following recommendations were made;

- i. that manufacturers of FMCGs add eco-awareness messaging into the packaging and marketing materials of their products in order to emphasise the environmental benefits of selecting sustainable products.
- ii. that companies are obligated to provide information that is both clear and succinct regarding the recyclability of the materials used for packaging and the appropriate methods for recycling or disposing of the material after it has been used.
- iii. that businesses carry out consumer research in order to gain an understanding of the visual preferences and perceptions of eco-labels among the target audience. This decision-making process would have a significant impact on the purchasing decisions of the individual.

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